

Original Article

Clinicopathological Correlation of Leiomyoma Undergoing Myomectomy in A Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate clinic pathological correlation of Leiomyomas undergoing myomectomy in tertiary care hospital.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Gynaecology and Obstetrics Department, Services Institute of Medical Sciences Lahore, from June 2019 to September 2022 on a sample of 123 eligible patients. After a detailed history investigations and clinical examination, e.g. CBC, blood grouping, fasting blood sugar, ESR, ultrasound scan, laparotomy was performed and the size of uterus, tubal and ovaries condition and total number and location of fibroids we noted. A tubal patency test using methylene blue was performed. Histopathological examination was performed to confirm any endometrial pathology or degenerative process. The data was analysed SPSS 21.0. Categorical variables like demographic profile, clinical characteristics, and location of myoma were presented as frequency and percentages.

Results: Mean age was 25.23±5.623 years. In the study population, 69.1% were nulliparous. Heavy menstrual bleeding was the commonest symptom, constituting 44.7%, mass in abdomen in 30.1%, infertility in 22% and dysmenorrhea in 3.3% cases. Most common site of leiomyoma was Intramural (51.21%), Subserosal 29.26%, and Submucous 19.51%.

Conclusion: The study concluded that leiomyoma is one of the most common diseases of reproductive age.

Keywords: Clinicopathological correlation, leiomyomas, fibroids, uterine fibroids.

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Introduction

Leiomyoma of uterus are benign tumors and one of

most prevalent pelvic tumors among women with a variable symptomatology. Their occurrence is one in every four or five women of reproductive age. The global incidence rate of leiomyoma is around 5–20%.¹ Clinically they are evident among 20-30% of women that are over age of 30 years and 75% of them are located in uterus.³ Leiomyomas are rare before menarche and mostly they are diagnosed in repro-

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ductive life. Leiomyomas have a propensity to regress after the menopause and usually they are correlated with endometrial hyperplasia. These findings are suggestive of their estrogen dependency in etiology.¹⁴ Uterine fibroids should be classified according to the location of these leiomyomas whether they are on serous surface, on the mucous membrane or in myometrium. This is due to the reason that most of the symptoms a women experience due to these fibroids depends upon and different according to the location of uterine fibroid. Also, the approach to the treatment varies and so is the outcome of treatment.^{1,2}

There are total of nine types of uterine fibroids as suggested by the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO). FIGO classification system divides leiomyomas into nine different types depending upon location among them 0–2 types are submucosal fibroids and type 3 fibroids is adjoining the endometrium but completely within the wall. Type 4 fibroids are a complete intramural myoma. Leiomyomas of Types 5-6 are present in the serous layer of endometrium, and type 7 fibromas are pedunculated and are present on the subserosal surface. Type 8 leiomyomas can be found in the ectopic locations such as the cervix, etc.³

Presenting complaints and symptoms in women can vary and usually related to size of tumor, location and number of Leiomyomas. Majority of them are symptomatic in early age and usually progression is slow and they grow with time.² The important symptoms of these leiomyoma abnormal uterine bleeding and present with abdominal pain and sense of pressure in abdomen. Fibroids large in size can cause a diffuse uterine growth with an irregular uterine contour of uterus resulting in infertility in

most of cases.⁴

Leiomyomas can be asymptomatic and diagnosed on routine ultrasound or they can present with a variety of clinical symptoms like pain, pressure sensation or abnormal bleeding. They represent a major public health burden due to their cost and impact on quality of life among women and constitute a major economic issue in the society. In developing countries like us they are one of important cause of subfertility and anemia among women.⁵ The gold standard of leiomyoma treatment is surgical intervention. Hysterectomy is the definitive surgical operation, but myomectomy is still commonly performed especially in women who desire future fertility. More recently developed techniques, which include uterine artery embolization (UAE), magnetic resonance-guided focused-ultrasound surgery (MRgFUS), and myolysis, are emerging as minimally invasive alternative procedures. To date, there is no definitive therapeutic agents for the treatment of uterine leiomyomas.^{6,7} This is of paramount importance that health authorities regarding maternal and child health should make new policies in early diagnosing and prevention of complication among women presenting with uterine fibroids and adopt strategies to treat them with less surgical intervention.

Methodology

A cross sectional study was conducted in the SIMS Hospital Lahore from June 2019 to September 2022. Total 123 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria, females under the age of 50 years undergoing myomectomy and exclusion criteria, females undergoing hysterectomy for fibroid uterus were selected through a non-probability consecutive sampling. Sample size was calculated with win pepi version 11.15 with

95% confidence interval and acceptable difference of 8% assuming 29% prevalence of leiomyomas. After a detailed history, investigations and clinical examination, e.g. CBC, blood grouping fasting blood sugar, ESR, ultrasound scan, laparotomy was performed and we noted the size of uterus, tubal and ovaries condition and total number and location of fibroids. For patients undergoing for myomectomy a tubal patency test was using methylene blue was performed. Histopathological examination was performed to confirm any endometrial pathology or degenerative process. The data was analysed SPSS

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of subjects

Variables (n= 123)	Frequency	Percent
Age (years) Mean±SD=25.23±5.623		
Min = 18 Max = 49		
18-30 years	41	33.4
31-49	82	66.6
Education		
Illiterate	53	43.0
Primary	52	42.2
Matric and above	18	14.8
Occupation		
House wife	109	88.6
Working	14	11.4
Residential status		
Urban	78	63.4
Rural	45	36.6
Parity		
Nulliparous	85	69.1
P1	12	9.8
Para 2 – 4	26	21.1
Menstrual Bleeding		
Heavy Menstrual Bleeding	55	44.7
Mass Abdomen	37	30.1
Infertility	27	22.0
Dysmenorrhea	4	3.3
Number of Fibroid		
1	64	52.0
≥1	59	48.0

21.0. Categorical variables like demographic profile, clinical characteristics and location of myoma were presented as frequency and percentages.

Results

Total 123 subjects were included in the study. Mean age was 25.23±5.623 years with minimum age of 18 years and maximum age of 49 years. Among them

Table 2: Location of Fibroids

Type of Fibroids	Single location	Multiple location	Total	Pearson chi-square P value
Intramural	29 (53.7%)	25 (46.3%)	54 (100.0%)	P = 0.933
Sub mucous	23 (53.4%)	20 (46.6%)	43 (100.0%)	
Sub serosal	15 (58.0%)	11 (42.0%)	26 (100.0%)	
Total	67 (53.2%)	56 (49.8%)	123 (100.0%)	

Table 2: Location of Fibroids

Characteristics	Type of fibroid (n=123)			P-value
	Intramural (n=54)	Subserosal (n=26)	Submucosal (n=43)	
Presenting complaint				
HMB	16 (29.6%)	8 (30.8%)	31 (72.1 %)	0.000
Mass abdomen	20 (37.0%)	14 (53.8 %)	3 (7.0%)	
Infertility	16 (29.6%)	4 (15.4 %)	7 (16.3 %)	
Dysmenorrhea	2 (3.8%)	0 (%)	2 (4.6 %)	

43.0% were illiterate and 42.2% were having primary education. Majority of the study population (88.6%) were housewife and 63.4% were living in urban locality. Nulliparous were 69.1% and 9.8% were primigravida. Heavy menstrual bleeding was the commonest symptom, constituting 44.7%, followed by mass in abdomen in 30.1%, infertility in 22% and dysmenorrhea in 3.3% cases. (Table 1). Most common site of leiomyoma was Intramural 43.90%, Sub mucosal were 34.95%, and Subserosal were 21.13% (Table 2). By comparing presenting complaint and type of fibroid (table 3) most

common cause of heavy menstrual bleeding is submucosal fibroid (56.36%), intramural fibroid 29.09% heavy menstrual bleeding, and subserosal fibroid in 14.54%.

Figure 1: Degenerative Changes

Discussion

The frequency of leiomyoma is highest during the third decade, Bhasker Reddy and Bulun SE in their study showed⁸⁹ that leiomyoma is a disease among women of childbearing age and usually less commonly seen before puberty or after menopause. In current study, out of 123 cases 85(69.1%) were nulliparous, multipara 26(21.1%) and primigravida 12(9.8%). In study done by Mangala Gowri et al¹⁰, out of 259 cases, 246(94%) were seen in multipara, followed by primipara 10(3.8%), and nulliparous 3(1.3%). In peri-menopausal women leiomyoma's are one of foremost important cause of morbidity. There is limited data regarding morbidity, clinical and pathological pattern of uterine leiomyoma's in our community. We conducted this study to evaluate the clinic pathologic spectrum, presentation, types and locations of uterine leiomyoma's and compare our findings with other similar studies from different regions.

The age of patients ranged from 18-49 yrs. Maximum number of patients included in this study were between 31 -40 years (59.34%). These findings were similar to that observed by Gupta et al.¹¹ (51.40%)

and Funaki et al (46.82%). In our study most common presenting complaint is menorrhagia, which is seen in 44.7%, followed by mass in abdomen (30.1%). In studies conducted by Usha, Gupta and Funaki K menorrhagia was also chief complaint 35.4% and 68.0% respectively.^{9,11,13}

In our research we included 123 cases of leiomyomas and among them, 67% were single and 56% were multiple, while Sarfraz et al in his study observed 60.9% of cases were of multiple leiomyomas¹² in regarding site the most common site of leiomyomas in our study was intramural (43.90%) followed by submucosal leiomyomas (34.95%). Subserosal (21.13%), These findings are similar to a study conducted by Mega Lahori in which 57.4% were intramural leiomyomas followed by subserosal leiomyomas constituting 30.7% and 8.9% were submucous and 3.0% were broad ligament leiomyomas.^{8,10,13-16}

Majority of the women (63.4%) were from urban similar to study done by Ngorilli et al in their study majority of the women were from urban area i.e. 57.2%. The reason may be due to greater access to health facilities, increase awareness regarding reproductive health.¹⁷

In our study, out of 123 cases, degenerative changes were seen in 14 leiomyomas, out of which 50% show hyaline degeneration followed by myxoid degeneration (28.57%), cystic (14.28%) and red degeneration (7.14%). Secondary changes were observed by Gowri et al in her study with 16.9% changes were of hyalinization being the most common change, 3.5% having secondary degenerative changes, 3.5% were of cystic type and 1.9% with myxoid change. The different approaches for clinical management of uterine fibroids should be customized based on specific presentation, location and symptoms also should be based on individual patient's needs and priorities. These leiomyomas are usually managed traditionally be surgery but this approach to treatment has inherent risks and complications after surgery. Non-surgical

treatment approaches have recently been adopted for management of these fibroids including medical therapies along with interventional radiology.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

Conclusion

The study concluded that leiomyoma is most common benign tumour of peri-menopausal age. Heavy menstrual bleeding, abdominal mass and infertility were the most common symptoms in our study. Menorrhagia was the most common presenting complaint caused by submucosal fibroid.

Conflict of Interest: *None*

Funding Disclosure: *None*

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Authors Contribution

TW: Conceptualization of study

JM, FA: Literature Search

JZ, AW: Statistical Analysis

UAW: Data Collection and Analysis

JM: Drafting, Revision

JM: Writing of Manuscript

All authors are equally accountable for accuracy, integrity of all aspects of the research work.